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Dendrimer as drug delivery tool

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Introduction: Dendrimers, are the three-dimensional, hyperbranched globular novel nano-polymeric system. The physiochemical characteristic of dendrimers as nanoscopic size, high degree of branching, aqueous solubility, biocompatibility, and great versatility structural modification attract the attention of researchers to apply as a platform for the transport of bioactive molecules and enhances the solubility of hydrophobic active drugs. In addition, the availability of multiple functional groups at the periphery and cavities in the interior and the control over the dendrimers' properties during their synthesis render them promising agents to use in several applications which makes them more promised amongst the available polymers (1, 2).

Methods: Dendrimers are commonly developed by a divergent method or a convergent method. The divergent approach begins from a multifunction core molecule i.e., from core to the surface and in convergent methods initiates with surface to core possessing one reactive and two dormant groups. It gives the F-1 (first generation) dendrimer. The periphery of the developed molecule is activated for conjugation with more monomers (1).

Results & Discussion: The analytical techniques are generally used to confirm the chemical composition, polydispersity, morphology, shape, homogeneity, reaction rate. molecular weights, scattering techniques, conjugation, structural deformities, and purity of dendrimers. These analyses include spectroscopic techniques, scattering methods, microscopic methods, electrical methods, chromatographic techniques, and physical or rheological properties analysis (4).

Conclusions: The applications of dendrimers have been explored in a variety of fields such as drug delivery, gene delivery, imaging, diagnosis and photodynamic therapy. The terminal functionalities of dendrimers provide a platform for conjugation of the drug and targeting moieties as drug delivery tools. Furthermore, their coating with ligand(s) may reduce their toxic side effects and other biological obstacles in targeting potent ingredients to the targeted site(s) of interest with their controlled release effectively. The varied characteristics make dendrimers a great choice for diverse applications (2,3).

Keywords: *Dendrimers, biocompatibility, drug-delivery, toxicity, targeting moieties*

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